

After school, the necessary functional maturity is achieved, that is, "school adulthood". "I don't know," he said, " but I'm sure you're right." But when you reach adolescence, you will have to pay for the crisis of that age and the accompanying neurosis. One of the problems that make it difficult to master the curriculum is somatic weakness. Teacher V. A. Sukhomlinsky, paying attention to the intellectual development and health of students, said that "slow thinking is the result of general morbidity."

Although the basis of the activity of a teacher – psychologist in schools is a short list of activities and tasks that are based on the development of students' personality, it is proposed to use a typological method in the practice of pedagogical and psychological service in schools, as it learns the characteristics of tasks, difficulties, problems, methods and methods of their solution that are characteristic of the educational period. The typology proposed by US allows us to develop more generalized strategies of professional, pedagogical and socio - psychological work (with respect to each individual), which are carried out with different groups of students (typical on a certain basis).

Psychodiagnostic and design methods of research differ from the typology (Kettel. The proposed diagnosis may be related to the formation of professional training in a higher educational institution, professionally significant qualities, and plans for the future based on personal requirements. Typological diagnostics the ability to solve various tasks of Student Life is based on the method of progressive, that is, open typology, in which the strategies chosen by him in solving various contradictions are supplemented by new knowledge about the individual based on feedback about his ability to participate in Student Society. Typological diagnostics treat student age as an age of reflection –not only their own personal qualities, but also the recognition of those qualities that were used in professional situations in reality life. Therefore, it can exist as a method of self-awareness, which cannot be used by diagnostic methods that require other, more complex explanations.

The concept of individual organization of time can include in itself the results of the study of the time Order of activity in various professions (for example, the French psychologist Sh. Godbua studied the mode of Organization of time for nurses working on a two-shift work schedule for 20 years). Some of the time modes of activity that occur in various professions are mentioned: the most popular is the time deficit (its lack in the performance of activities) Limit Mode (where the subject must perform the work under certain pressure, expedited to complete the work on time), the mode in which the term of completion of the service is not specified (found in the creative professions of writers, artists, scientists), the Effective Time Mode in the implementation of the work (average standard), etc. in the course of studying how different subjects work in a certain mode of activity, it was found that the most important factor in the organization of a person's time is the transfer of time internally or externally.

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FEATURES OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract the desire of a teenager to be independent, to give birth under the care of adults is found in all children, and a number of them read fantastic literature day and night, imitating their characters.

During the extracurricular period, a teenager learns radio engineering and electrical engineering. "I don't

know," he said. (for example: boys tease girls by pulling their hair.B) but the same teenager tries to behave culturally in front of unfamiliar adults. Teenagers are usually described as a difficult age to raise. The first thing to consider is that the psyche changes its behavior in the past, and new qualities arise from it.

Key words: adolescence, personality, education

One of the most noticeable structures associated with adolescence is a very strong desire for self – education. The active process of self-education begins at this age and usually continues in some form throughout a person's later life. By the beginning of self-education in adolescence, we mean the fact that for the first time a child at the age of 12-13 has intellectual opportunities and thoughts about self-improvement (self-improvement) of personality. That is, we mean that the child takes conscious and purposeful actions to achieve this goal. Adolescence is referred to in the relevant literature as "difficult", "changing", "transition age". In the latter case, at the "transition age", the adolescent moves from childhood to adulthood. A teenager is more talkative than other young people, and often goes up to teachers and relevant literature. Because at this stage, the specifics of his mental development are much different from those of an adult with a young child. Another characteristic feature of this period is that the teenager wants to do everything on his own and get rid of the advice of the mind under the patronage of older people. The difference between a teenager and an adult is not only that he has different relationships with older people, but also that he has a wide range of biological development (puberty, etc.). And in general, the teenager has a different character. For example, when a teenager is in the lower class, he can only memorize the homework assignment, and at a young age, he tries to express the homework in his own words. Some teenagers at this stage, when communicating with people older than their former position, are friendly, polite, and now have the ability to behave rudely, that is, to violate order. From the definition of this problem, there is a dispute among researchers. However, this feature of the psyche is probably due to the peculiarities of social life in adolescence. When a teenager protests that I can do everything myself, "you still think I'm a child," he still can't do much. In other words, a teenager is a child in terms of mastering the case, and an adult in terms of claims. Adolescence is the same characteristic of adolescents of both present and past eras. At the same time, modern teenagers are not old enough to meet the demands of older people. Because, first of all, today, most students, including teenagers, often do not have any other tasks that they are engaged in studying. We have already taken into account that in previous eras, a child from a younger age was used to producing material goods (grazing livestock, mowing fire or hay). "I don't know," I said. On the contrary, parents release a teenager from household chores, saying that he will not be able to complete an educational task. And the transition from adolescence to adulthood is psychologically a new quality, but the reason for this transition is the consequences of mental development: if adults consider a teenager a child, on the contrary, they consider themselves mature. This discrepancy between the two can also affect the development of adolescence. The desire of a teenager to be independent and give birth under the care of adults is found in all children, and a number of them read fantastic literature day and night, imitating their characters. During the extracurricular period, a teenager learns radio engineering and electrical engineering. "I don't know," he said. (for example: boys tease girls by pulling their hair.B) but the same teenager tries to behave culturally in front of unfamiliar adults. Teenagers are usually described as a difficult age to raise. The first thing to consider is that the psyche changes its behavior in the past, and new qualities arise from it. Sometimes such a change can occur in a short time. (but change does not occur in adolescence at the same time.) Secondly, due to the emergence of such a new branch of the psyche, the child suffers from anxiety, which prevents him from getting used to education. Psychologists prove such changes differently. At the beginning of this century, psychologist Z. Frith explained that a teenager does not give in to the care of adults, "an unconscious hobby caused by sexual qualities that say that I do everything myself." This opinion is opposed by many psychologists. The unwillingness of teenagers to be brought up is not final, but one of the times when they meet temporarily. The social environment has a great influence on the upbringing of a teenager. Depending on the specifics of the development of society, the requirements for young people are constantly changing. In accordance with this requirement, the state of society affects him differently from

don't know, and I don't know, and I don't know, and I don't know. It is important to remember that our ancestors have long revered the concept of heroism, which is inherited from grandfather to son.

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BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA O'QITUVCHI VA O'QUVCHI ORASIDAGI MULOQOT VA SHAXSLARARO MUNOSABATNING AHAMIYATI

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Ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida muloqot va shaxslararo munosabatlar tushunchasi shunchalik ahamiyatli, unda o'qituvchi va o'quvchilarning birgalikdagi faoliyatlari ehtiyojlaridan kelib chiqadigan turli faolliklari mobaynida bir-birlari bilan o'zaro munosabatlarga kirishish jarayoni yuzaga keladi.

Ya'ni, har bir insonning jamiyatda bajaradigan faoliyatlari (mehnat, o'qish, o'yin, ijod qilish va boshqalar) o'zaro munosabat va o'zaro ta'sir shakllarini o'z ichiga oladi. Chunki har qanday faoliyat odamlarning bir-birlari bilan til topishishlarini, bir-birlariga turli xildagi ma'lumotlarni uzatishlarini, fikrlar almashinuvi kabi murakkab hamkorlikni talab etish bilan birga bir shaxsning jamiyatda tutgan o'rnini, ishlarining muvaffaqiyatini, obro'si uning muloqotga kirisha olish qobiliyatini belgilaydi.

Bir qaraganda oddiygina ko'ringan shaxslararo muloqot aslida juda murakkab jarayon bo'lib, unga inson hayoti mobaynida ko'nikma hosil qilib o'rganib boradi. Aslida muloqotning psixologik jihatdan murakkab ekanligi haqida B.F. Parigin shunday yozadi: «Muloqotshunchalik ko'p qirrali jarayonki, unga bir vaqtning o'zida quyidagilar kiradi:

- a) individlarning o'zaro ta'sir jarayoni;
- b) individlar o'rtasidagi axborot almashinuvi jarayoni;
- v) bir shaxsning boshqa shaxsga munosabati jarayoni;
- g) bir kishining boshqalarga ta'sir ko'rsatish jarayoni;
- d) bir-birlariga hamdardlik bildirish imkoniyati;
- ye) shaxslarning bir-birlarini tushunishi jarayoni».

Har bir insonning ijtimoiy tajribasi, uning insoniy qiyofasi, fazilatlari, hattoki, nuqsonlari ham muloqot jarayonlarining mahsulidir. Jamiyatdan ajralgan, muloqotda bo'lish imkoniyatidan mahrum bo'lgan odam o'zida individ sifatlarini saqlab qolishi mumkin, lekin u shaxs bo'lolmaydi. Shuning uchun muloqotning shaxs taraqqiyotidagi ahamiyatini anglashmaqsadida uning bir qancha vazifalarini tahlil qilib chiqamiz.

Har qanday muloqotning eng **oddiy vazifasi** - suhbatdoshlarning o'zaro bir - birini tushunishlarini ta'minlashdir. Bu milliy urf-odatlarimizdagi salom - alik, hol-ahvol so'rash, hurmat ko'rsatib, ochiq yuz bilan kutib olish kabi muomala vositalaridir. Halqimizning eng qadrli xususiyatlaridan biri uyiga kelgan insonni samimiy tarzda ochiq yuz bilan kutib olib, ko'rishidir.

Muloqotning **ikkinchi muhim vazifasi** ijtimoiy tajribalarga asoslanish bo'lib, bunda oila va qarindoshlar davrasida ijtimoiylashuv asosida insonning o'zida zarur xarakter xususiyatlarni shakllantirishdan iborat. Har bir inson avvalo o'z oilasida shaxs sifatida kamol topadi. Ilk ta'lim va tarbiyani oilada oladi.

Muloqotning uchinchi vazifasi - u insonni ma'lum bir faoliyatga tayyorlaydi, o'rgatadi, ruhlantiradi. O'zaro muloqot va muomalaga kirishishdan uzoqlashgan odamlar ongida rivojlanish kuzatilmaydi, ularning jamiyat uchun foydasi ham sezilmaydi. Ularda maqsadli